

TILSHUNOSLIKNING AMALIY MASALALARI: ZAMONAVIY TILSHUNOSLIKNING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI, YECHIMLARI, TARAQQIYOTI VA ISTIQBOLLARI

mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman

MATERIALLARI

2025-yil 29-30-sentabr

**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY TA’LIM, FAN VA
INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI
SIRDARYO VILOYATI HOKIMLIGI
GULISTON DAVLAT UNIVERSITETI,
TURKIYA RESPUBLIKASI BALIKESIR UNIVERSITETI,
TURKIYA RESPUBLIKASI FIRAT UNIVERSITETI,
YANGLING KASB-HUNAR VA TEXNIKA KOLLEJI**

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Tahrir hay’ati:

A.Axrorov, A.Mamatqulov, Sh.Ro‘ziqulov, Z.To‘ychiyeva

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METHODOLOGY OF USING TERMINOLOGICAL DICTIONARIES IN TEACHING BIOLOGY SUBJECTS

Hasanova Amalia Murad,

ORCID: 0000-0002-2196-3215

PhD in Biology, Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University,
Baku, Azerbaijan, amalya.hasanova59@mail.ru

Abstract. In the process of shaping biolinguistic thinking in the teaching of biological sciences, there are serious problems related to the spelling and pronunciation of globally accepted terms. The use of linguistic research to study how language shapes thinking is considered a relevant requirement of the times. And biological research is used to study the neural and genetic basis of language and other cognitive abilities. Biolinguistics is defined as the study of the evolution of biology and language. Interdisciplinary communications using different fields such as biology, linguistics, psychology, anthropology, mathematics and neurolinguistics are used to shape language. Although there is much scientific evidence of the influence of environmental factors on language through behavioral studies, little information exists on the influence of environmental factors on the neurobiology of language development. Practical classes on linguistics and speech culture in biology majors should consider the peculiarities of terminological work of students of biology majors. Specialists teaching this discipline, taking into account the biological profile,

should teach future teachers and scientific researchers the role and necessity of scientific style of speech in the study of biological terms.

At present, some previously accepted ideas are being revised in biological education, which, in turn, confirms the need to improve and further develop the methodology of studying and teaching modern views on the theory of evolution. Therefore, the selection of the content and development of the methodology of studying Charles Darwin's theory of natural selection in pedagogical universities and school biology course are relevant. Teaching Charles Darwin's theory of natural selection, genetics of heredity, genetic diseases in pedagogical universities and school biology course requires a high level of linguistic knowledge and strict terminological knowledge. Teaching the provisions of the struggle for survival, one of the theories underlying biological sciences, should also be based on the methodology of correct use of special terms. In teaching this subject, the study of natural and artificial selection should be accompanied by evidence of the leading role of evolution. Characterizing the struggle for survival as an evolutionary factor, it is necessary to emphasize its ecological nature. When explaining the consequences of natural selection, it is necessary to take into account their cause-and-effect relationships, to teach this topic with practical examples, using various textbooks and assignments.

Keywords: biological sciences, biological terms, evolutionary theory, natural and artificial selection, interdisciplinary integration.

INTRODUCTION

A biology teacher should know the important directions of biological sciences covering living nature. In today's education system, genetic engineering, bionics, new views on evolutionary teaching and integration of various branches of cytogenetics occupy a wide place in the teaching of biological sciences. Disciplines such as cytology, molecular biology, plant physiology, microbiology, evolutionary teaching, anthropology, developmental biology, and biogeography are rich in biological terms, and each has already established its place in biological science.

In all modern education systems, the subject of neurocomputing technology, biotechnology, is taught in biomedical education. This subject teaches the basics of human life activity, human adaptation to the environment, artificial intelligence and robotics created in accordance with the neural structure of the brain. It should be noted that biological sciences are taught using STEAM technology as a basic science [1].

Bionics is the science of applying the organization, biotechnical properties and structure of living nature in technical devices and systems, which directly contributes to the formation of STEAM-knowledge.

Biological bionics studies the processes occurring in biological systems, and theoretical bionics creates mathematical models of these processes. Technical bionics applies theoretical bionics models to engineering problems (navigation and electronics, development of prostheses, etc.). Bionics is applied in the framework of the project "Living Prototypes of Artificial Systems". With this in mind, learning and pronunciation of terms in the process of teaching biological sciences shapes the student's worldview.

METHODS

Biology is rich in complex terminology requiring memorization and learning of various concepts. Teaching and using these terms requires strict discipline. There are a large number of terms of foreign origin in all areas of biology, so students must understand the meaning of the terms and pronounce them correctly. Biological concepts should be purposely parallel in terms of their translation into Azerbaijani, understanding the essence of the concept and the definition of the concept. Therefore, in order to facilitate memorization and understanding of complex and voluminous factual material in biology, the teacher needs to study specific methods. Besides, students of biological specialty should know the peculiarities of scientific style of speech, peculiarities of formation of scientific thinking with its help. Under the scientific style is understood a functional style, reflecting the communicativeness, implying the function of language, corresponding to the goals and objectives of certain spheres of communication. Scientific style includes varieties that create specificity in biological literature.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The difficulty of mastering biological terminology is due to the large volume of many topics, as well as the need to use terms of “bilingualism”, equivalents of foreign language origin - systole, diastole, etc. Greek-Latin terminological elements. For example, the terminological element logos (science) - mycology (the science of fungi), algology (the science of algae), cytology (the science of cells), ornithology (the science of birds), etc. The Romanization of countless scientific fields emphasizes the importance of addressing the spelling and pronunciation of these words. Of course, regardless of the country of teaching, the Greek-Latin terminological elements are used in the same way internationally. New terms are constantly appearing due to the development of botany and zoology, as well as microbiology. Studying the structure of motivation structure of subject teaching, the appropriate use of biological terms provides the formation of intellectual outlook of students, including schoolchildren [2].

The rate of speech development varies considerably among the younger generation, and this variability is the result of a complex interaction of genetic and environmental factors. There is very little data specifically explaining the contribution of genetic and epigenetic factors to the neurobiology of language, as well as to the neurobiology of language development. Based on our experience in biology classes, it can be noted that zoological, anatomical, microbiological, etc. concepts require serious study of the peculiarities of terminological work. Therefore, there are serious problems in improving the terminological vocabulary of biology students [3].

The fields of biological sciences are not limited to those listed above. Since this science is the science of life, the living world and the struggle for existence, biological sciences form the basis of medical sciences. If terminological issues are given an important place in the study of biology, it is possible to clearly convey the essence of the material presented [4].

In many cases, students cannot explain the content of a concept defined by a particular term; moreover, they often misspell the terms. Sometimes textbooks that do not explain concepts clearly enough are to blame. The lack of systematic work with terms at lessons also has an impact. In the course of zoology students are faced with new words, which are not always clear and difficult to memorize. To work with terms, students are recommended to compile explanatory dictionaries to work with educational and popular science literature.

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THE DISSEMINATION OF ECOTERMS IN MULTICULTURAL AND GLOBAL COMMUNICATION: LANGUAGE, CULTURE, AND SOCIAL IDENTITY PERSPECTIVES

Nigar Murvat Khanaliyeva,
Master's Student, Faculty of Philology
Sumgait State University
xanaliyeva999@gmail.com
0009-0001-9032-4732

Abstract. This study examines ecoterms in globalization and multicultural contexts, showing that they convey ecological knowledge, cultural identity, and global communication. Analysis of online platforms and academic publications reveals that ecoterms act as tools of communication and cultural codes, especially for younger generations as markers of ecological awareness and identity. They also demonstrate variation across educational and professional groups, where ecoterms are used either for social identification or for technical and scientific exchange. The study emphasizes their relevance for language policy, intercultural dialogue, and cultural exchange, highlighting their role as expressive instruments of social interaction rather than mere terminological units.

Keywords: Ecoterms, Multiculturalism, Global communication, Language and culture, Social identity